

A STUDY ON EMPOWERMENT OF WOMEN THROUGH EDUCATION

Vidyashri C Halakerimath* & Shivagangamma B. Danappagoudra**

* Faculty, Journalism and Mass Communication Department, Rani Channamma University, Belagavi, Karnataka

** MHScholar, Extension and Communication Management, RHSc, University of Agricultural Sciences, Dharwad, Karnataka

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Abstract:

Indian constitution guarantees equal rights to women with men through various provisions. However, even after sixty plus years of democratic experience the male dominated Indian society is not ready to accept the women on par with them in different walks of life. Consequently, women in India in general and the rural India in particular have been undergoing a lot of sufferings. Understandably, women are responsible for bearing children, but most of the rural women are malnourished and poor in health. Further, the rural women are over working at home –looking after the children, preparing food for all at home, cleaning the home and vessels apart from working in the field or in the land lord's house as part time laborer. At home, in the poverty ridden rural India, most of the men eat major portion of the scarcely available food prepared by their life partners and the women have to satisfy with the left out. The situation is causing a lot of damage to the pregnant women. Of course there is legal guarantee for female education in India but in practice only thirty eight per cent girls attend the primary schools. This is mainly because of the negative opinion of the parents and the society. So we tried to study the situation and conducted a research in and around Hubli-Dharwad and selected the respondents through random sampling research method. The total sample size was 50.

Key Words: Education, Empowerment, Knowledge & Women

Introduction:

Education:

According to Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia, education in the largest sense is any act or experience that has a formative effect on the mind, character, or physical ability of an individual. In its technical sense, education is the process by which society deliberately transmits accumulated knowledge, skills and values from one generation to another. There is legal guarantee for female education in India but in practice only thirty eight per cent girls attend the primary schools. This is mainly because of the negative opinion of the parents and the society as follows.

- ✓ First, most of the uneducated and daily wage parents feel that they will get nothing in return, in a short term or long term, by educating their daughters.
- ✓ Secondly, girls alone attend the household related routine works for both the parents have to attend other outside works.
- ✓ Thirdly, they feel that there is insecurity in the school because of the male dominated teaching community. Parents are worried about the 54 chastity of their daughters and they feel that home is a safer place than the school.
- ✓ Fourthly, the distance between the school and the house and lack of free transport facilities in many villages also discourage the parents to send their girls to schools.
- ✓ Fifthly, the responsibility of looking after the young ones at home compel them to attend the child care work as the parents have to go for their daily works to earn their livelihood. This responsibility of looking after their younger sister or brother forces the senior but young girls to forgo their educational ambition.
- ✓ Sixthly, no guarantee of job even after successfully completing their schooling or no possibility of getting free admission in higher educational institutions also discourage the poor parents from sending their girls to the schools.

Empowerment:

According to Business Dictionary, empowerment means, "A management practice of sharing information, rewards, and power with employees so that they can take initiative and make decisions to solve problems and improve service and performance. Empowerment is based on the idea that giving employees skills, resources, authority, opportunity, motivation, as well holding them responsible and accountable for outcomes of their actions, will contribute to their competence and satisfaction".

There are other definitions of empowerment as: "The term empowerment refers to a range of activities from individual self-assertion to collective resistance, protest and mobilization that challenge basic power

relations. For individuals and groups where class, caste, ethnicity and gender determine their access to resources and power, their empowerment begins when they not only recognize the systemic forces that oppress them, but act to change existing power relationships. Empowerment, therefore, is a process aimed at changing the nature and direction of systemic forces that marginalize women and other disadvantaged sectors in a given context. "It is giving lawful power or authority to act. If people were empowered they would be able to participate in the planning, execution and implementation of developmental schemes. Apart from Political Empowerment, Economic and Social Empowerment are crucial. Empowerment and development are closely related. Empowerment leads to development, which further leads to greater empowerment".

Women Empowerment:

According to UNESCO, women empowerment means the following:

- ✓ Having decision-making power of their own
- ✓ Having access to information and resources for taking proper decision
- ✓ Having a range of options from which you can make choices (not just yes/no, either/or.).
- ✓ Ability to exercise assertiveness in collective decision making.
- ✓ Having positive thinking on the ability to make change.

According to U.N. women Empowerment means, "What, then, is women's empowerment? Women's empowerment has five components:

- ✓ women's sense of self-worth;
- ✓ their right to have and to determine choices;
- ✓ their right to have access to opportunities and resources;
- ✓ their right to have the power to control their own lives, both within and outside the home; and
- ✓ their ability to influence the direction of social change to create a more just social and economic order, nationally and internationally .6

Empowerment of women is a complex concept encompassing physical, social, economic and political aspects. Particularly after the declaration of 1976-85 as the decade for women by the United Nations, question of empowering women as equal partner in all walks of life becomes a critical issue throughout the world. Women empowerment means giving powers to women. Giving them importance can be called as women empowerment. The word 'women empowerment' essentially means that the women have the power or capacity to regulate their day to day lives in the social, political and economic terms, a power which enables them to move from the periphery to the centre stage. Self-decision regarding education, participation, mobility, economic independency, public speaking, awareness and exercise of rights, political participation and many more factors ensure women empowerment. In short, women empowerment is the breaking of personal limitation.

Review of the Related Literature:

Review of literature is the base for deciding the research problems, selecting objectives and formulating hypothesis. It can never be undertaken in isolation of the work that has already been done on the problem which is directly or indirectly related to a study proposed by a researcher.

- ✓ Jain. Ambika, (1991) made a study on "Analysis and evaluation of the animators training camp for the education and empowerment of rural women conducted by IIE, 1988-1989 and the major findings were- i) Ignorance amongst the rural women was found to be the dominant feature. ii) Awareness was generated amongst the women on health, nutrition, mother-child care, land regulations and legal rights for women through the programme. iii) Women developed self confidence through the programme and felt that they should participate in community development programmes of the village and iv) They realized the importance of girls education.
- ✓ Jamir. S C, (2005) made a study on "Empowerment of socially and economically weaker section of the society through University". From the study it was found that apart from the economic and social inequalities, another form of inequality that is deeply entrenched in our country that is the one based on "Gender". Universities can play a transformative role in empowering women, making them aware of their rights and enabling them to show as enlightened and confident women.
- ✓ Janaki. D, (2006) in his study " Empowerment of women through Education : 150 years of University Education in India found that Education will be used as an agent of basic change in the status of women. The concept of equality, opportunity and education touches every aspect of women's lives social, political and economic.
- ✓ Jumani. Usha, (1991) conducted a study to analyze the status of self-employed women in rural areas. Economic activities through which the income of the women will be increased have to be identified with great care.
- ✓ Kalita. Sri Gangeswar, (2011) made a study on "Participation of women in politics in Goalpara District of Assam". The findings of the study were that ,lack of literacy facility, Natural inconveniences, poverty stricken difficulties, communication inconveniences, averse topological conditions,

heterogeneous land conditions, the people of Goalpara District particularly women community is marching upward in different field, particularly in politics is hopeful.

- ✓ In the work of Kane. W, Emily and Kyyro, K, Else, (2001). For “whom does Education enlightened Race, Gender, Education and Beliefs about social inequality”? It revealed that education is positively associated with four questions addressing affirmative action, suggesting that education may empower them to endorse this group based remedy for social inequality.
- ✓ Karlekar. Malavika, (2004), on “A note on the empowerment of women” and attempted to trace a brief history of empowerment and its implications for Indian women. The Essay showed that the instruments for empowerment have to contend with entrenched prejudices and patriarchal modes of oppression. Women will garner confidence and men will learn to accept that power is not a male prerogative.
- ✓ Kakati. Dr. Kunja Kusum, in 1995 studied about the education of women and social change- A case study in two villages of Barpeta District. The field work was done during October and November, 1995. Main findings of the study were --
 - It provides no discrimination between boys and girls in respect of education. But it will merely be a concept if the women themselves don't perceive the need for it.
 - In the investigation a great discrepancy was found between the educated and uneducated respondents in their attitude towards equality of educational facilities for boys and girls. Their parents did not motivate them .It was their peer group and their brothers in several cases ,who encouraged them to go to vocational education .
 - The out of school girls simply got into the vocational education being pursued at home because they had to make a living.
- ✓ Khaire. Rupali Jitendra, (2011) made a study on “Literature review of the women Entrepreneurs and Statutory Policies”. The article helps to investigate how women entrepreneurship has developed into an accepted concept which makes an important part of the economy. Here the investigator aims to review the critical points of current knowledge including substantial findings through secondary sources.

Research Methodology:

The study was conducted in and around Hubli-Dharwad. And for this study the selection of respondents was through random sampling method. The total sample size was 50 and only women. The collected data were tabulated, analyzed by using frequency, percentage, index and correlation.

Result and Discussion:

Table 1: General information about respondents n=50

S.No	Variables	Category	Respondents	
			Frequency	Percentage
1.	Age			
		Young (18 – 35 years)	42	84
		Middle (36 – 55years)	8	16
		Old (> 55 years)	-	-
2.	Caste			
		Forward caste (GM)	18	36
		Other backward caste	15	30
		SC	07	14
		ST	10	20
3.	Education			
		High school (class 8 -10)	12	24
		College and above (PUC & above)	38	76
4.	Type of family			
		Nuclear	35	70
		Joint	15	30
5.	Family size			
		Small family (1-4)	28	56
		Medium family (5-8)	10	20
		Large family (9 and above)	12	24
6.	Family occupation			
		Agriculture	25	50
		Employee	15	30
		Others	10	20

Table 1 refers to the general information of the respondents indicated that large majority (84.00%) of the respondents were belongs to 18 to 35 year age group and 16.00 percent of the respondents were belongs to 36 to 55 year age group. With respect to caste 36.00 percent of the women belong to forward caste (GM) and

30.00 percent belong to OBC, 20.00 percent of the respondents belong to ST and 14 percent belong to SC. With respect to education of the respondents 76.00 percent respondents women completed PUC and above education and followed by 24.00 percent were completed education up to high school. With respect to type of family, 56.00 percent of the respondents belong to nuclear family and remaining respondents belong to joint family. Regarding family size, 56.00 percent of respondents have small family size followed by 24.00 percent belong to large family and remaining belong to medium family. With respect to family occupation, 50.00 percent of the respondents belong to agriculture family followed by 30.00 percent belong to employee family and remaining 20.00 belong to other occupation.

Table 2: opinion of women about social empowerment of women

S.No	Social Empowerment Variables	SA		A		UN		DA		SDA	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1	Attainment of Higher Education has helped women in achieving special status in the society	10	20	25	50	15	30	-	-	-	-
2	Higher educated women are respected by their husband's family	20	40	20	40	-	-	10	20	-	-
3	Higher educated women should not question the domestic violence (e.g beating wives) done by men to their wives	-	-	-	-	10	20	25	50	15	30
4	Higher education has enabled women to access information, knowledge to participate in the society.	15	30	35	70	-	-	-	-	-	-
5	Higher Education has enabled women to cope up with their in laws family	22	44	26	52	4	8	-	-	-	-
6	Higher education enables women to marry whom she likes	10	20	20	50	-	-	20	40	-	-
7	Higher educated women are aware of government welfare programs for women and childhood	12	24	38	76	-	-	-	-	-	-
8	Higher educated women are aware of reproductive rights, nutrition, healthcare, child care and family planning.	17	34	26	52	7	14	-	-	-	-
9	Higher educated women can adjust/balance with their family problem.	11	22	25	50	-	-	14	28	-	-
10	Social concern is higher among the more highly educated	15	30	20	40	-	-	15	30		

Table 2 depicted the opinion of women about social empowerment indicated that fifty and more than fifty percent of women were agreed with statements like Higher educated women are aware of government welfare programs for women and childhood(76.00), Higher education has enabled women to access information, knowledge to participate in the society(70.00), , Higher educated women are aware of reproductive rights, nutrition, healthcare, child care and family planning(52.00), Higher education enables women to marry whom she likes(50.00), Higher educated women can adjust/balance with their family problem(50.00) , Attainment of Higher Education has helped women in achieving special status in the society(50.00) and Social concern is higher among the more highly educated (40.00) by reviewing all these statements educating women in higher level improve the social participation and improve status of women followed by half of the women were disagree with higher educated women should not question the domestic violence (e.g beating wives) done by men to their wives because educated women were against the violence done by men because its more harm to women mental and physical health.

Table 3: opinion of women about Educational empowerment of women

S.No	Educational Empowerment Variables	SA		A		UN		DA		SDA	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1	Higher education has enhanced the outlook of women towards self and self esteem	10	20	35	70	5	10	-	-	-	-
2	Higher education trains women to acquire good decision making capacity	20	40	20	40	10	20	-	-	-	-
3	Higher education enable women to perform as excellent leaders at all levels	15	30	25	50	10	20	-	-	-	-
4	Higher educated women think that they are intellectually equal to higher educated men	10	20	35	70	5	10	-	-	-	-
5	Higher education encourages women's creative thinking	15	30	28	56	-	-	7	14	-	-
6	Higher educated women have significant autonomy in decision making at home and workplace	18	36	32	64	-	-	-	-	-	-
7	Higher educated women utilize their given resources and opportunities properly	10	20	30	60	10	20	-	-	-	-
8	Higher educated women can bring content life	17	34	26	52	-	-	7	14	-	-
9	Higher educated women are courageous to protest against sexual abuses	16	32	34	78	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	Commitment and competency are high among the higher educated women	15	30	20	40	15	30	-	-	-	-

Table 3 interpreted the opinion of women about educational empowerment and results revealed that more half the women were agreed with statements like Higher educated women are courageous to protest against sexual abuses (78.00), Higher education has enhanced the outlook of women towards self and self esteem and Higher educated women think that they are intellectually equal to higher educated men (70.00), Higher educated women have significant autonomy in decision making at home and workplace(64.00), Higher educated women utilize their given resources and opportunities properly(60.00) followed by near half and half of the women were agreed with statements like Higher educated women can bring content life(52.00), Higher education enable women to perform as excellent leaders at all levels(50.00), Higher education trains women to acquire good decision making capacity (40.00) and Commitment and competency are high among the higher educated women. By observing all the above statements concluded that education provide knowledge of good decision making skill and management of resources. Education also created awareness of opportunity to develop and to lead happy life in the community.

Table 4: opinion of women about Psychological empowerment of women

S.No	Psychological Empowerment Variables	SA		A		UN		DA		SDA	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1	Higher education is the major cause for women's upliftment in our society	10	20	25	50	15	30	-	-	-	-
2	Women need to go beyond Higher Education	20	40	20	40	-	-	10	20	-	-

3	Higher education motivates women to postpone their age for marriage and gap between two children	-	-	25	50	10	20	15	50	10	30
4	Higher education motivated women to balance between domestic work and career work	10	20	35	70	5	10	-	-	-	-
5	Higher education can reduce marital conflicts between the couple	15	30	24	48	4	8	7	14	-	-
6	Housewives with higher education are better in home management than those without education	10	20	20	50	-	-	20	40	-	-
7	Higher educated women play multidimensional role at home and society	18	36	20	40	-	-	12	24	-	-
8	Higher education reduce female infanticide	17	34	26	52	-	-	7	14	-	-
9	Higher education brings environmental awareness and protection among women	16	32	22	44	12	24	-	-	-	-
10	Higher education makes woman to be more cautious about their health and beauty	-	-	20	40	15	30	15	30		

Table 4 shows that opinion of women about psychological empowerment indicated that 70 percent of respondents were agreed with higher education motivated women to balance between domestic work and career work. half of the respondents were agreed with statements like Higher education is the major cause for women's upliftment in our society, Higher education motivates women to postpone their age for marriage and gap between two children, Housewives with higher education are better in home management than those without education and Higher education reduce female infanticide (52.00) followed 40 percent of the respondents were agreed with statements like Higher education can reduce marital conflicts between the couple(48.00) Higher education brings environmental awareness and protection among women(44.00), Higher education makes woman to be more cautious about their health and beauty , Women need to go beyond Higher Education and Higher educated women play multidimensional role at home and society. Education improved thinking capacity of women and develops confidence among them. Education also provides stress free and happy life in the society.

Table 5: opinion of women about Economic empowerment of women

S.No	Economic Empowerment Variables	SA		A		UN		DA		SDA	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1	Higher educated women are as capable as other men in making successful careers	12	24	38	76	-	-	-	-	-	-
2	Men could share and involve in women's spending decisions	14	28	23	46	-	-	13	26	-	-
3	Higher educated women have economic independence than illiterate women	10	20	34	78	-	-	6	12		
4	A good higher educated women should hand over her income as it is to her husband	10	20	22	44	-	-	11	22	7	14
5	Higher education has enabled women to access government loans, schemes and employment opportunities	-	-	35	70	15	30	-	-	-	-
6	Higher educated women's savings could enable them to initiate their own income-generating activities	-	-	42	84	8	16	-	-	-	-
7	Awareness of consumerism and its rights are more among higher educated women	-	-	28	56	12	24	10	20		

8	Higher educated women have more saving consciousness for their family	9	18	36	72	-	-	5	10	-	-
9	Higher educated women should have independent bank transactions using cards	-	-	35	70	15	30	-	-	-	-
10	Higher educated women shows greater interest in generating income and assets	-	-	25	50	14	28	11	22	-	-

Table 5 predicated the opinion of women about economic empowerment and result revealed that majority of the respondents agreed with statements like Higher educated women's savings could enable them to initiate their own income-generating activities (84.00%), Higher educated women have economic independence than illiterate women(78.00%), Higher educated women are as capable as other men in making successful careers (76.00%), Higher educated women have more saving consciousness for their family(72.00%), Higher education has enabled women to access government loans, schemes and employment opportunities(70.00%) and Higher educated women should have independent bank transactions using cards (70.00%) followed by more than half of the respondents agreed with statements like Awareness of consumerism and its rights are more among higher educated women(56.00%) and Higher educated women shows greater interest in generating income and assets(50.00%) .

Result and Discussion:

From the results we concluded that educating women in higher level improve the social participation and improve the status of women and education provide knowledge of good decision making skill and management of resources. Education also created awareness of opportunity to develop and to lead happy life in the community. Education improves thinking capacity of women and develops confidence among them. Education also provides stress free and happy life in the society.

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